

ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY TEST OF ANDALIMAN FRUIT ESSENTIAL OIL (*ZANTHOXYLUM ACANTHOPODIUM* DC) AGAINST *SHIGELLA DYSENTERIAE* AND *ESCHERICHIA COLI*

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ABSTRACT

Diarrhea is an increased frequency of defecation more than three times a day with liquid feces, often caused by microbes such as *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella dysenteriae* bacteria. This research aims to test the antibacterial activity of andaliman fruit essential oil (*Zanthoxylum acanthopodium* DC.) against *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella dysenteriae* as well as analyzing the composition of chemical compounds in the essential oil using the GC-MS method. Essential oils are isolated using water distillation. Characterization of essential oils was carried out by determining specific gravity, refractive index, and GC-MS analysis. The results showed that the essential oil yield was 0.02% (v/w), the specific gravity was 0.8226 g/ml, and the refractive index was 1.465. GC-MS analysis identified 25 chemical compounds with the main components based on relative levels being Linalool 36.82%, Geranyl benzoate 17.91% and γ -Terpinene 7.78%. From the results of the

antibacterial activity test of essential oils, the average inhibitory diameter against *Shigella dysenteriae* bacteria at concentrations of 20%, 40%, 60% was 8.73 mm \pm 0.46; 12.56mm \pm 0.21; 15.33 mm \pm 0.51, while for *Escherichia coli* bacteria the average inhibitory diameter at concentrations of 20%, 40%, 60% was 8.96 mm \pm 0.56; 11.43mm \pm 0.74; 14.53mm \pm 0.65. This research supports the potential of andaliman fruit as an antibacterial source.

KEYWORDS: Andaliman (*Zanthoxylum acanthopodium* DC), Essential oil, *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella dysenteriae*.

INTRODUCTION

Diarrhea is an increase in the frequency of bowel movements, occurring more than three times a day, and the stool consistency becoming watery (Nurhayati, 2020). Diarrhea is a major killer of children, accounting for approximately 8 percent of all deaths among children under 5 years of age worldwide. Most deaths from diarrhea occur among children under 5 years of age living in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa (UNICEF, 2021). Diarrhea is endemic in Indonesia and a potential outbreak (KLB) disease that is often accompanied by death (Hajiri & Asih, 2023).

Diarrhea is generally caused by several microbes, including bacteria. The most common bacteria causing diarrhea are *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella dysenteriae* (Koletzko & Osterrieder, 2009; Saeed *et al.*, 2015). *Escherichia coli* is a normal flora in the digestive tract which can sometimes become pathogenic if the number of bacteria increases or when the body's immune system is weakened, while *Shigella dysenteriae* is a bacteria that causes pathogens in humans. *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella dysenteriae* are able to produce toxins that bind to the intestinal mucosa, causing diarrhea (Brooks *et al.*, 2012).

Diarrhea caused by *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella dysenteriae* bacteria can generally be treated with broad-spectrum antibiotics such as ciprofloxacin, co-trimoxazole, and erythromycin (Setiati *et al.*, 2014). However, the irrational use of antibiotics can pose a new health problem (Adrian *et al.*, 2023). The use of antibiotics that do not comply with therapeutic guidelines will increase the development of bacterial resistance to antibiotics (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2011).

One of the plants that has the potential as an antibacterial is andaliman (*Zanthoxylum acanthopodium* DC.), which is a spice plant that is widely found in North Sumatra. Andaliman fruit (*Zanthoxylum acanthopodium* DC.) contains compounds that have antibacterial activity. Andaliman fruit essential oil contains compounds such as limonene, linalool, and α -pinene, which have strong antibacterial activity (Fitri *et al.*, 2021).

Research conducted by Yasni (2001) showed that there are 11 active components of andaliman essential oil, with 5 main components, namely apinene, limonene, geraniol,

citronellol, and geranyl acetate. These essential oil components can inhibit the growth of bacteria (*Pseudomonas*, *B. cereus*, and *S. aureus*) and mold (*Fusarium* sp, *Penicillium* sp, and *Aspergillus flavus*). The results of antimicrobial testing in Siswadi's research (2002) showed that the essential oil of andaliman fruit is bactericidal against the bacteria *Bacillus stearothermophilus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Vibrio cholera*, and *Salmonella thypimurium*.

Nabila (2023) stated that andaliman fruit essential oil has antibacterial activity against clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus epidermidis* with an average inhibition diameter of 19.8 ± 2.08 mm, 13.6 ± 1.15 mm, 11.4 ± 0.6 mm, 10.3 ± 0.4 mm, 9.8 ± 0.06 mm, 9.3 ± 0.52 mm at concentrations of 25%; 12.5%; 6.25%; 3.125%; 1.56%; and 0.78%.

Yasni (2001) stated that 7.15% (w/v) of andaliman fruit essential oil was effective in inhibiting Gram-positive bacteria (*Bacillus cereus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative bacteria (*Pseudomonas*) as well as inhibiting several types of mold such as *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium* and *Fusarium*.

Fitri *et al* (2021) stated that Andaliman fruit essential oil has antibacterial activity against *Streptococcus mutans* bacteria at a concentration of 40% with an inhibitory diameter of 14.5 mm and against *Propionibacterium acne* bacteria at a concentration of 40% with an inhibitory diameter of 14.1 mm.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research Sample

A 1 kg sample of andaliman fruit was taken from the Panei Tongah area, Panei District, Simalungun Regency, North Sumatra. The part taken was the andaliman fruit (*Zanthoxylum acanthopodium* DC.), and the collection was done manually.

Andaliman Fruit Distillation

After removing dirt, 1 kg of Andaliman fruit was weighed and placed in a steam distillation apparatus. It was then heated to a boil, allowing steam to rise. Distillation took place at 80-100°C for 3-4 hours. The distillate of essential oil was separated using a separating funnel to separate the water from the remaining oil. Store in a tightly closed brown bottle, protected from light, covered with aluminum foil, and stored at room temperature (Febrianti *et al.*, 2019).

Essential Oil Evaluation

Specific Gravity

Specific gravity is a quantity that states the ratio between mass (g) and volume (ml), so the specific gravity unit is g/ml. Determination of the specific gravity of a liquid using the Pycnometer method, where the weight of the empty Pycnometer and the Pycnometer containing essential oil is first weighed. The difference from the weighing is the mass of the liquid at room temperature (25°C) and in constant volume, stated on the Pycnometer, then the specific gravity of the liquid is the mass divided by the volume of the Pycnometer, with units of g/ml (Januarti, 2009).

Refractive Index

Water is passed through the refractometer until the temperature matches the reading. The temperature should not differ by more than $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ from the reference temperature and must be maintained within a tolerance of $\pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$. Before the oil is placed in the instrument, it must be at the same temperature as the measurement, which is 20°C. Readings are then taken when the temperature has stabilized (Rini *et al.*, 2018).

GC-MS

The chemical components of essential oils can be determined using a GC-MS (Gas Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry) instrument. The method of implementation is that the GC-MS equipment that will be used for GC will be operated at a temperature of 60°C for 4 minutes, then the temperature is increased to 120°C with a temperature increase of 2°C per minute. At 120°C, the temperature is maintained for 5 minutes, then the temperature is increased again with a temperature increase of 50 °C per minute to a final temperature of 290°C, and then maintained for 10 minutes. For the total gas flow rate used is 50 ml per minute with a slit ratio of 1:30, the injector temperature is 300°C, and the amount of sample to be injected through the injector is 0.1 µl. Meanwhile, for MS, the electron energy used is 70 eV with an accelerating voltage of 1.30 kV. The mass range detected ranges from 40-400 µg/mol with a scanning interval of 1 second (Nurhaen *et al.*, 2016).

Preparation of Media

Sterilization of Tools

The glassware used in this antimicrobial activity study was first sterilized using an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes, tweezers were burned by burning over direct flame, and the media were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes (Katili *et al.*, 2020).

Nutrient Agar Media

Weigh 5 grams of Nutrient Agar (NA) powder. Add 250 ml of distilled water and heat until dissolved. Then, sterilize in an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes. After sterilization, allow the temperature to cool to approximately 45°C. The media is ready to be poured into petri dishes.

Bacterial Rejuvenation

Bacterial rejuvenation was performed using the streak method. Pure cultures of *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Escherichia coli* were taken from one loop and inoculated aseptically onto NA media. The samples were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Making Mc. Farland Solution

A 9.95 mL 1% H₂SO₄ solution was mixed with 0.5 mL 1% BaCl₂ solution in an Erlenmeyer flask. The solution was then shaken until a cloudy solution formed. This turbidity was used as the standard turbidity of the test bacterial suspension (Muljono *et al.*, 2016).

Making a Bacterial Suspension

A 24-hour-old bacterial culture was taken from the agar slant. 2 loops of test bacterial colonies were suspended in 10 mL of sterile 0.9% NaCl in a sterile test tube. Then homogenized by vortexing. Turbidity was compared with Mc. Farland by measuring the transmittance value using a UV-vis spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 600 nm (Muljono *et al.*, 2016).

Antibacterial Activity Test

A total of 15 mL of Nutrient Agar (NA) was placed into a sterile petri dish, then 100 µL of the test bacterial suspension was added. Then, the petri dish was homogenized by shaking the media. The media was allowed to solidify. Sterile discs were soaked in various concentrations of essential oils: 20%, 40%, and 60%. A 5 µg/disk ciprofloxacin disc was placed on the surface of the media as a positive control and a DMSO disc as a negative control. Then, it was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. This treatment was repeated 3 times. Then, antibacterial activity was determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone formed using a caliper (Muljono *et al.*, 2016). The provisions for the strength of the inhibition area are as follows: an inhibition area of 20 mm or more means very strong, an inhibition area of 10-20 mm (strong), an inhibition area of 5-10 mm (moderate) and an inhibition area of 5 mm (less) is said to have no effect (Davis & Stout, 1971).

Data analysis

The data obtained are displayed in tables and figures. The diameter of the inhibition zone was measured using the inhibition zone area calculation formula (Andini & Sri Sayekti, 2020).

$$\text{Area of inhibition zone} = \frac{(AB)+(CD)}{2}$$

Note:

AB = Vertical

CD = Horizontal

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The yield of andaliman fruit essential oil was 0.02 % (Table 1). Nabila (2023) stated that the yield of andaliman fruit essential oil was 1.77 %. The specific gravity of andaliman fruit essential oil was measured using a 10 ml pycnometer. Specific gravity is the ratio between the weight of an oil sample and the volume of oil at the same temperature (Maradesa *et al.*, 2014). The principle of measuring specific gravity is to compare the weight of the sample to the weight of water at the same temperature and volume. The results of the measurement of the specific gravity of andaliman fruit essential oil were 0.8226 g/ml (Table 1). According to Fitri *et al* (2021), the specific gravity value of andaliman fruit essential oil was 0.8880. The resulting andaliman fruit essential oil did not differ much from previous researchers.

The refractive index of andaliman fruit essential oil was measured using a refractometer. The refractive index is the ratio of the speed of light in air to the speed of light in the substance at a given temperature. The refractive index of essential oils is closely related to the components of the resulting essential oil. Similar to specific gravity, the components of an essential oil can affect its refractive index (Jayanudin & Hartono, 2011). The refractive index value in this study was 1.465 (Table 1). Fitri *et al.* (2021) stated that the refractive index of andaliman fruit essential oil was 1.4665.

Table 1: Results of Evaluation of Andaliman Fruit Essential Oil Components.

No.	Evaluation	Results
1	Yield	0.02% (v/w)
2	Specific Gravity	0.8226 g/ml
3	Refractive Index	1,465

Andaliman fruit essential oil was tested using a GC-MS tool to see its chemical components. Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) is a combination of gas chromatography

and mass spectrometry. The GC-MS results obtained from the study were 25 compounds consisting of α -Terpinene; Benzene, 1,3-diethyl-; Linalool; Geranyl benzoate; p-Cymene; 3-Cyclohexene-1-acetaldehyde, α ,4-dimethyl-; Retinol; Tridecane; Heptadecane; cis-9-Tetradecen-1-ol; Hydroperoxide, 1-methyl-1-phenylethyl; Retinal; Oxacyclododecan-2-one; Dodecanoic acid, methyl ester; Dodecanoic acid. The GC-MS results on essential oils showed that the main components of andaliman fruit essential oil compounds based on relative levels were Linalool 36.82 %, Geranyl benzoate 17.91% and α -Terpinene 7.78%.

In this study, DMSO 10 μ L was used as a negative control and a positive control used ciprofloxacin disc 5 μ g/disc. From the research that has been done, it is known that the positive control (ciprofloxacin 5 μ g/disc) has an average inhibitory diameter greater than the bacteria *Shigella dysenteriae* of 27.68 mm and *Escherichia coli* of 27.24 mm, this value is greater than the average inhibitory value of essential oils. This is because ciprofloxacin works to slow and stop the development of bacteria. Negative control (DMSO) does not provide inhibitory power because DMSO will not interfere with the observation results, because it does not provide activity against bacterial growth. From the results of testing the antibacterial activity of andaliman fruit essential oils by the diffusion method, the average inhibitory diameter against *Shigella dysenteriae* bacteria at concentrations of 20%, 40%, 60% was 8.73 mm \pm 0.46; 12.56 mm \pm 0.21; 15.33 mm \pm 0.51, while against *Escherichia coli* bacteria, the average inhibition diameter at concentrations of 20%, 40%, and 60% was 8.96 mm \pm 0.56; 11.43 mm \pm 0.74; 14.53 mm \pm 0.65 (Table 2). From the results of the research that has been done, it can be concluded that the essential oil of andaliman fruit at concentrations of 60% and 40% is included in the strong category, while the concentration of 20% is included in the moderate category against *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Escherichia coli* bacteria.

Table 2. Results of Antibacterial Activity Tests Against *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Escherichia coli* Bacteria.

Sample	Concentration	Average diameter of inhibition \pm SD	Average diameter of inhibition \pm SD
		<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Andaliman fruit essential oil	20%	8.73 \pm 0.46	8.96 \pm 0.56
	40%	12.56 \pm 0.21	11.43 \pm 0.74
	60%	15.33 \pm 0.51	14.53 \pm 0.65
Control (+) (ciprofloxacin 5 μ g/disc)		27.68	27.24
Control (-) (DMSO)		0	0

The results of the study showed that the antibacterial activity of Andaliman fruit essential oil was higher against *Shigella dysenteriae* bacteria than *Escherichia coli*. Although both bacteria are gram-negative, they have differences, especially in their ability to deal with antibacterial substances. *Escherichia coli* bacteria have a special ability in their extracellular components that can bind iron (siderophore) so that they can extract Fe³⁺ from lactoferrin (or transferrin), which provides iron to cells for growth. This can be used for defense against bactericidal substances. The advantages possessed by *Escherichia coli* bacteria result in differences in the clear zones that are formed. The clear zone in *Escherichia coli* bacteria is formed smaller than the clear zone in *Shigella dysenteriae* bacteria (Aini, 2017).

Based on the research results, Andaliman fruit essential oil can inhibit the growth of *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Escherichia coli* bacteria. This is thought to be influenced by the secondary metabolite compounds contained in Andaliman fruit essential oil.

The process of bacterial inhibition by essential oils occurs due to their ability to bind to extracellular proteins and bacterial cell walls. The more lipophilic, the more they can disrupt the bacterial cell membrane. The inhibitory mechanism is thought to be through the destruction of the lipid bilayer of the cell membrane due to its hydrophobic groups (Mulyani & Gunawan, 2010). Meanwhile, according to Bakkali *et al* (in Dewi, 2015) the mechanism of action of essential oils in killing bacteria is by changing the permeability of the cell membrane, eliminating ions in the cell, blocking the proton pump, and reducing the production of adenosine triphosphate (ATP). Linalool is a terpenoid alcohol. Terpenoid alcohols can inhibit bacterial growth activity through the mechanism of bacterial protein denaturation (Permatasari *et al.*, 2015).

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